

ÉTS
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Mechanical Sieving of Carbon-Fibre/PEEK Prepreg Trim Waste and its Influence on Compression Moulded Panel Properties

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Tape Edge Trim (TET) Waste

- Non-uniform prepreg edges slit and chopped
- Chopping facilitates handling and reduces process interruption
- Waste rate estimated at 4.5 % to 5.4 % based on 12 in. rolls

Video source <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=VYtRlnRLh1U>. Converted to GIF using VEED.io

Tenax®-E TPUD PEEK-HTS45

Tape Edge Trim (TET) Waste

CARBON FIBERS | THERMOPLASTICS

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Inside Teijin's thermoplastic tape expansion

Teijin is qualifying its second thermoplastic tape line in Heinsberg, Germany, that will significantly expand the company's presence in this material segment.

#workingprogress

JEFF SLOAN
Editor-in-Chief, *CompositesWorld*

notes. The total capacity of the line varies by the areal weight of the material being produced, but ter Steeg reports that the system, at maximum throughput and maximum areal weight, can produce up to 320 metric tons per annum.

How many production lines & materials exist globally?

PEKK

LM PAEK

PEEK

PPS

PEI

Toray Advanced Composites

Strand-based Compression Moulding Compounds

Smith (2021). DOI: [10.13140/RG.2.2.31101.44002](https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.31101.44002)

Control Arm
Feraboli et al. (2011)

Complex Demonstrator
Greene (2014)

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Challenges of Direct TET Compression Moulding

- *Low Energy Process*
- *High-performance Constituents*
- *Known History*
- *Low Contamination*

- *Variable Strand Geometry*
- *Unknown Resin\Fibre Content*
- *Uncertain Production Volume*

Objectives

- Characterize strand geometry
- Perform mechanical sieving to reduce TET variability
- Manufacture panels from sorted and unsorted TET
- Measure resulting panel thickness and warpage
- Evaluate flexural properties

Image Analysis Tool

Python Code

- Length
- Width
- Area
- Aspect Ratio

Baseline Strand Characteristics

66.8 % by no. of strands
68.0 % by area of strands

	Mean, "x"	Median, "	IQR (50 %)	Min	Max
Length	19.5 mm	14.9 mm	8.4 – 27.3 mm	0.1 mm	55.8 mm
Width	16.5 mm	13.8 mm	8.0 – 23.4 mm	0.0 mm	46.4 mm
Aspect Ratio	1.23	1.16	0.91 – 1.44	0.11	2.23

Mechanical Sieving

20 mm

14 mm

5 mm

2.5 mm

Effect of Sieving on Strand Geometry

TET Panel Manufacturing

Moulding Parameters

Dwell temperature: 400 °C

Consolidation pressure: 1 MPa

Dwell time: 30 min +/- 10 min

Slow cooling at 3-5 °C/min

Tooling Info.

Material: Invar 36

Cavity size: 30.5 cm x 30.5 cm

LMG 150-ton Press

Panel Quality Evaluation

Visual

Canon DSLR + 105 mm Sigma

3D Scan

Hexagon 85 Absolute Arm

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Panel Thickness Variation

- No correlation observed between sorting and panel thickness
- 2.60 – 3.82 mm avg. thickness range
- Avg. panel COV 5.33 %

Panel Quality Evaluation

Flexural Properties

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